

INFLUENCE OF INTERWOVEN CONFIGURATION
ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CROSSED
HELICOIDAL FILAMENT WINDING COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A comparison is made of results obtained for the elastic constants of crossed helicoidal filament-wound composites with the same angle of winding and different interweaving of the fibres.

When interweaving increases the values of elastic constants raise up to a stabilization level. The elastic matrix is found to tend progressively towards symmetry which does not occur in configurations interwoven to a small degree.

INTRODUCTION

Filament winding is one of the most flexible and automated manufacturing processes for large composite structures. Production of complex parts is now possible by using multiaxial manufacturing equipments (with several degrees of freedom) which allow one-directional bands to follow paths programmed in accor-

dance with the shape of those parts and with loads that correspond to their operating conditions.

Shells built through these processes have a composition that varies through their thickness according to the points considered on their surface. In fact, they are not laminated media, since there is no continuous superposition of plies, which interweave following more or less complex configurations.

The mechanical characterization of these media presents considerable intricacies, and at present there is not such theory as to describe it satisfactorily. As a rule use is made of models based on the theory of laminated media, so neglecting the influence of ply interweaving. The main purpose of this work is to assess the importance of errors produced by the use of this type of models for glass-fibre composites.

For simplicity, the scope of this preliminar study was limited to the classical winding process of circular cylindrical shell fabrication - unidirectional band winding onto a rotational mandrel with translational movement of the part guiding reinforcement laying.

In this case the problem that stands out relates to the different more or less interwoven crossed helicoidal configurations that may be obtained. For the same angle of winding, these different configurations may be characterized by the ratio N between the pitch of the helices and the band width, as Figure 1 shows.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to determine the dependence of elastic behaviour upon the ratio N , samples were produced for values of $N = 1, 2, 5$ and 10 , the first case corresponding to a true laminate. The

Figure 1 - Different configurations in crossed helicoidal filament winding

diameter of the pipes was 100mm, and for practical reasons a 64° winding angle in relation to the axis was chosen. Owing to limitations of the capacity of the test equipment, the pipes were constructed in such a way as to superpose only two one-directional plies at each point, at symmetrical angles. As a result of the interweaving, the sequence order varies between $/ +64/ -64/$ and $/ -64/ +64/$ from point to point, at an increasing frequency as N augments.

Although the configuration with $N = 1$ corresponds to anti-symmetric angle-ply laminate, in order to evaluate the differences of properties between the different configurations suf -

fice to adopt for all of them a model of macroscopically homogeneous and orthotropic single ply.

The elastic behaviour in plane stress can be characterized by means of axial tension, internal pressure and torsion tests, which make it possible to determine the longitudinal modulus E_{11} and hoop modulus E_{22} and the corresponding Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{21} , as well as the shear modulus G_{12} . These elastic constants were determined for all configurations by using the tubular specimen testing technique already described¹.

The basic idea behind the development of this testing technique was to avoid the usual locking-ring jaws used in tension and biaxial tests, which produce considerable constraint in radial displacement, thus replacing it by a tensioning system resting on eight discrete points arranged regularly along the perimeter, the same load being applied to them. Figure 2 shows the tubular specimen (a) and its setting in a biaxial (tension - internal pressure) test (b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Important differences in stiffness were observed for the different configurations in all the above mentioned tests, as Figure 3 shows for the internal pressure case.

The elastic properties obtained from experimental plottings are tabulated below.

The results display some dispersion due to defective preparation of the specimens. In addition to the difference in glass content shown in the table, there was some irregularity in the positioning of fibres as a result of their having been processed in industrial machines prepared for large structures, which are not precise enough for the 100mm diameter chosen for the spec-

a)

b)

Figure 2 - Tubular specimen used for elastic moduli determination

TABLE 1 - Elastic properties of different filament winding configurations

Configuration (Parameter N)	Glass content (%)	ENGINEERING CONSTANT (GP _a)				
		E_{11}	ν_{12}	E_{22}	ν_{21}	G_{12}
N = 1	70	11.9	0.29	28.6	0.55	9.5
N = 2	68	10.6	0.29	29.5	0.52	9.2
N = 5	72	13.8	0.24	32.4	0.44	10.2
N = 10	75	13.6	0.20	31.6	0.42	10.5

imens. Our laboratory is not provided with means of specimen construction and so we have to resort to industrial machines, the only available in the country.

In spite of the above difficulties, the results clearly point

Figure 3 - Comparison of experimental data in internal pressure tests

to increase of the elastic and shear moduli, and to decrease of Poisson's ratio as interweaving augments. The slight decrease of E_{11} and G_{12} when N passes from 1 to 2 can be attributed to a decrease in the fibre content. The slight differences between the properties of pipes with $N = 5$ and those with $N = 10$ seem to indicate that the properties stabilize as soon as a given degree of interweaving has been attained.

Other important conclusion is that the elastic moduli and the Poisson's ratios, determined in redundancy, do not fulfil the interdependency relationship required by symmetry of the matrix of elasticity. Besides as interweaving increases the trend to symmetry becomes more and more marked. Similar conclusions

have already been reported by other authors, for example by Bert and Guess² who also presented an interesting discussion on this subject. We believe, however, that non-symmetry is mainly a consequence of the impossibility of defining a volume element representative of the material in poor interwoven configurations.

CONCLUSIONS

Summing up: as interweaving increases the behaviour of the helicoidal configurations progressively goes from that of anti-symmetric angle-ply laminate to the behaviour of a macroscopically homogeneous and orthotropic material with higher overall stiffness in tension and shear. Rupture of specimens of each type under internal pressure further showed that strength also increases together with interweaving.

It would be of interest to quantify the above conclusions, however the quality of the specimens does not allow this to be made. This paper only reports a first step in a research program whose principal aim is to obtain a mechanical model of filament-wound composite materials including viscoelastic, fatigue and hygrothermal behaviour aspects. Intensive experiment, using different fibres and matrix, is needed in order to ensure sufficient universality to such a model.

REFERENCES

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- 2 - BERT, C. W. and GUESS, T.R., "Mechanical Behaviour of Carbon/Carbon Filamentary Composites", in Composite Materials: Testing and Design - Second Conference, ASTM - STP 497, pg. 89-106.